

Review Report

Fabric Designing Dexterity Improvement of Home-Economics Students for Boosting their Finances in Southeast Nigerian Universities

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Abstract: The aim of TVE to equip students with the necessary skills for self-reliance and poverty reduction calls for upgrading the skills imparted to students to keep them abreast of dynamic changes in today's world. This study therefore identified different skills in fabric designing Home-Economics students need to enhance their dexterity prowess for self-reliance and poverty reduction. To carry out this research, four research questions were raised and answered using means and mean differences. The study employed the descriptive survey research design. 100 lecturers and 340 final year students of universities that offer home economics education in the five states of the south-eastern geopolitical zone of Nigeria formed the population of the study. No sampling for the population was manageable. A questionnaire of two-scale components for possessed and needed fabric designing skills constructed and validated by experts was used for data collection. The reliability coefficients of the questionnaires were 0.823 and 0.723 respectively for the two scale components. The data analyses revealed knitting by machine, piping skill and other five novel fabric designing skills that are needed by home-economics students for poverty reduction and boosting of the students' finances. It was recommended that the integration of 21st Century Skills in Thematic learning also consistent workshops and conferences should be made mandatory for students to attend amongst others.

Keywords: Clothing and Textiles, Dexterity, Fabric Designing, Home-Economics students, University Education.

1. Introduction

Dexterity, which means the readiness in physical activity, especially skill, and ease in using the hands is the application stage depicting that a student excels in a skill. In teaching a skill, the emphasis is on practicing the skills and improving on the skill to form a habit. Dexterity skill is the ability to perform tasks expertly. It is an organized sequence of actions and proficiencies executed and usually displaying a flexible but, systematic patterning. According to (EijalGul, 2014), in teaching a skill, the emphasis is on constant practicing of that specific skill and having an improvement of the skill to make it habitual. Also, to possess a skill is to demonstrate the habit of acting and behaving in a specific activity in an individual through repetition or practice. Skill development is very important because it helps one to exhibit a measurable level of acquisition in a particular task or group of tasks. Oke&Olakotan (2017) asserted that the development of skills acquired and their improved sustainability creates room for enhancing of individual's intrinsic potential. The students need sustained ability and encouragement to rise to the dexterity level by overcoming the challenges inherent in skills acquisition processes. To this effect, Osuala (2016; 2004) pointed out that most technical skills training presents challenges to the learner by integrating practical work, theoretical knowledge, common sense, observation ability, and encouragement in an occupation. According to Bush, (2014), skill acquisition is the process of being trained in a specific task or function until expertise is developed. Also, the acquisition of skills has explicitly shown itself as one of the societal priorities due to its undeniable impact on advancing socioeconomic well-being. Thus, one of the ways these skills can easily be imbibed into the students is through university education.

University education is the type of education that provides the necessary skills through teaching the learners to enable them to become the manpower force of the nation's cultural, economic, and technological growth. According to S.O. Chukwuedo et.al (2014), university education is the level of education where specialization is highly emphasized because it is seen as the terminal point of formal education where students can have a good transition professionally from school to work. According to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013), as documented in the national policy on education (NPE), university education aims to cultivate a highly skilled workforce that aligns with the nation's needs by offering comprehensive and varied programs, thereby contributing effectively to national development. Thus, university education is pivotal in every aspect of a nation's development. Another goal of the university education as stipulated in the NPE document is to make entrepreneurial skills acquisition a requirement for all Nigerian universities. All these goals are achievable by emphasizing dexterity in every course taught at the university. One of those courses that ensures dexterity students offer in university is Home Economics education.

Home economics is an academic discipline that deals with how individuals families and communities relate within and amongst themselves and also the environment in which they live. As a unique and dynamic field of study, it has its central theme hinged not only on the improvement of the lives of individuals, families, and communities but also on the world. (Caroline F. A, 2015) stated that Home Economics encompasses a body of theoretical knowledge in both the exact sciences and humanities, as well as practical applications supported by suitable technologies. Home Economics is

a vocational subject included in the Nigerian Educational system, especially in most universities. Home Economics Education is a skill-focused subject that emphasizes decision-making, and tends to improve the employability skills of learners by equipping them with skills and knowledge that will earn them self-employment and at the same time, contribute effectively to the socio-economic development of the family and society. As a vocational subject, it has skill-based areas like foods and nutrition, home management, child development, clothing, and textiles amongst others.

Clothing and Textiles is an area of home economics that is concerned with teaching the students characteristics of different fabrics, designing, sewing, and reasons for the choice of clothes. It also involves the knowledge of the different textiles, principles of clothing selection and maintenance, interior decoration, etc. Clothing and Textile education is an area of home economics that teaches the acquisition of specific skills for self-employment or career skills in clothing-related instruction for example clothing and textile construction, maintenance and care, Knitting, crocheting, darning, dressmaking, laundry as well as working in the clothing and textile industries. Fadipe, (2022) stated that clothing and textiles education is one of the skill-based subjects that greatly harnesses an individual's productivity and also has a great impact on human development and economic growth. Yarmi, (2017) opined that clothing and textiles as an area of home economics expose students to a diversified curriculum. As a skilled subject, clothing, and textiles have different skill-based areas which are all designed to provide students with skills needed for fabric composition, clothing selection, home sewing and mending, clothing design and production, personal hygiene, good grooming, and preparing the students for working in textile and clothing industries. The different skill-based areas include; garment making, pattern drafting, soft furnishing/interior decoration, laundry, dry cleaning, and fabric decoration amongst others,

Fabric decoration which is one of the skill-based areas of clothing and textiles is the ornamenting of the surface of a fabric or garment. It is the patterning of an essentially plain fabric to render it more appealing or to serve decorative purposes. Also, fabric decoration is essentially creating designs for plain, woven, knitted, or printed or surface ornamented fabrics. This ornamentation of the fabrics usually consists of the repetition of patterns and is achieved through so many methods such as dyeing, appliqué, affixing sequins, rhinestones, use of lace, weaving, printing, embroidery, and designing amongst others.

Fabric designing is the concept of selecting, arranging, and ordering ideas for functional or ornamental purposes. It is the art of applying design and aesthetic concepts to fabrics. A good design creates beauty in the finished product. It involves careful and knowledgeable manipulation of art elements to produce expressive personal ideas through the application of design. Osifeso, (2001) outlined types of designs into two, namely; structural and decorative designs. She stated that structural designs may be made directly by pressing and matting fibers such as barkcloth and felt while decorative designs may be made by looping, knitting, knotting, netting, braiding, weaving, or plaiting. Fabrics that are made by these techniques are constructed by interworking one single set of elements or more. Elements of design which include line, color, texture, etc, and principles of design which include balance, rhythm,

proportions, etc all have effects and play huge parts and are to be considered while designing a fabric. There are other designs made on fabric like knitting which is the method of making fabrics by interlocking yarn loops through the use of knitting pins or needles to form chains of connected loops., crocheting which is a process of constructing fabrics by creating loops to form chain from a simple yarn, using a hook or needle, embroidery which is patterns that are sewn onto fabric using threads of various colors., sequins, lace, etc and all these require skills in producing them. All these skills in fabric designing when taught to home economics students can make them self-reliant and tackle financial distress to a very large extent which in turn helps in achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 1(No Poverty), goal 2(Zero Hunger) and goal 4(Quality Education).

1.1. Statement of Problem

Financial distress which is a condition in which an individual/family is unable to generate sufficient revenues or income to meet up with their financial obligations, is ravaging society, especially in this era of post covid. To tackle this financial distress, it is pertinent that students are imbued with the necessary skills for employment, self-reliance, and even employers of labor. In today's world, merely having a degree is no guarantee of employment, nor is it a reliable indicator of the individual's competence in a job. Rather, graduates must have current and relevant knowledge, practical experience, soft skills, and a positive attitude to allow them to be competitive in the job market. There is a need therefore for the type of education that equips students for self-employment. Fabric designing as one of the skills in clothing and textiles should be capable of equipping Home Economics students with saleable skills that will empower them to become self-employed, self-reliant, and competitive in the world market, it is therefore pertinent that varied skills in fabric designing are identified, ways of tackling hindrances to acquiring these skills to improve Home-economics students' skill acquisition in fabric designing be identified also to help make them self-employed thus self-reliant. They therefore formed part of the population for this present study.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this research is to: investigate the fabric designing improvement of home economics students for boosting their finances in south-eastern Nigerian universities. Specifically, the study investigated:

- (a) Fabric designing skills possessed and needed by students in Universities in South-East Nigeria.
- (b) The hindrances to acquiring these fabric designing skills
- (c) Ways of curbing these hindrances to improve students' skill acquisition in fabric designing

1.3. Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- (a) What are the fabric designing skills possessed and needed by students in Universities in South-East Nigeria?
- (b) What are the hindrances to acquiring these fabric designing skills?
- (c) What are ways of curbing these hindrances to improve students' skill acquisition in fabric designing?

1.4. Theoretical Framework

Skill theory was propounded by Cratty (1973). This theory anchors on the point that the level of practical skill performance is largely dependent on the occupational information given to the learners and the application of the knowledge required. Cratty further explained that the rate of practice and experiences of the students depends largely on the ability to comprehend and interact with various training resources such as human resources, facilities, tools, and equipment. This study is therefore significant to Cratty's theory in the sense that there is a need for constant improvement on the various skills students are exposed to to improve their level of skill performance, especially in a vicinity(Southeast) where fabric sales, decoration, and utilization are prevalent.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

The descriptive survey research design was employed in the study to collect data from lecturers and final students of home economics, textiles unit of fine and applied arts, and home science departments of five universities offering clothing and textiles.

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

The research project received ethical approval from the department of Home- Economics and Hospitality Management Education, textiles units of Fine and Applied Arts, and Home Science and Management in all the university under study. Informed consent was obtained from the project participants.

2.2. Area of the Study

The area of the study was five South-East Nigerian Universities offering clothing and textiles.

2.3. Population and Sample

The population of the study was 400 which was made of two categories of respondents. The first category comprised 340 final-year students offering either Home Economics, Home science, or textile major/fashion and designing students in Fine and Applied arts in the five universities. The second category was made up of all the 60 lecturers in the clothing and textile units of home economics, the textiles unit of fine and applied arts, and the Home Science departments of the five universities. The entire population was used because the population is of a manageable size.

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection and Study Procedure

A structured questionnaire was used for data collection. It was designed into Group A and Group B. Group A had item with two categories of response scales possessed and needed. The possessed category scale had four-point response scales of highly possessed (HP), averagely possessed (AV), slightly possessed (SP), and not possessed (NP), which was meant to determine the extent of the fabric designing skills possessed by Home-Economic students. The needed category scale had a four-point response scale of highly needed (HN), averagely needed (AN), slightly needed (SN), and not needed(NN), designed to seek information on the extent fabric designing skills are needed by home

economics students. All these four-point response scales had corresponding nominal values of 4, 3, 2, 1 respectively. Group B had items with a 4-point scale of strongly agree (SA), agree (A), disagree (D), and strongly disagree (SD) designed to seek information on ways fabric designing dexterity of home-economics students can be improved. The response scales had nominal values of 4, 3, 2, 1 respectively. Comments and suggestions were used in modifying the questions and items.

2.5. Data Collection Technique

The administration and retrieval of the instruments were done physically by the researcher and also using online goggle form. The goggle form link was sent to the respondents through some contact persons in the different university under study.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

The data was analyzed using mean and mean differences to answer research question one, while mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions two and three. In taking a decision, for research question one, the following steps were followed:

- The weighted mean value of each of the items of the extent of fabric designing skills possessed by home economics students (X_p) was calculated and the weighted mean value of each of the items of the extent of fabric designing skills needed (X_n) was calculated.
- The calculated mean difference (X_d) which is the difference between X_n and X_p was used for decision making. Thus;
 - Where (X_d) is positive (+), it means that X_n is greater than X_p . Thus fabric designing skill is needed.
 - Where (X_d) is negative (-) it means that X_n is lesser than X_p . Thus, the fabric designing skill is not needed.
 - Where (X_d) is 0, it means that the skill is not possessed nor needed by home economics students.

In deciding on research questions two and three, the mean and standard deviation were obtained using SPSS 20.0. A mean rating of 2.50 was used in making a decision. Items with a mean rating of 2.50 and above were upheld while items with mean ratings of 2.49 and below were not upheld.

3. Results and Discussion

Table 1: Analysis of the responses of the students on the skills in fabric designing possessed and needed by Home Economics students in South East Nigeria Universities.

S/N Fabric Designing Skills	\bar{X}_n	\bar{X}_p	$\bar{X}_d = \bar{X}_n - \bar{X}_p$	Decision
1. Sketching a desirable design	1.63	3.66	-2.03	NN
2. Knitting by hand	1.70	3.86	-2.16	NN
3. Knitting by machine	3.95	1.26	2.69	SN
4. Use of computer-aided design (CAD) in creating designs	3.70	1.48	2.22	SN
5. Piping skill	3.81	1.58	2.23	SN
6. Use of stencil in transferring Design	1.63	3.66	-2.03	NN
7. Fringe trimming skills	3.70	1.48	2.22	SN
8. Draft pattern designs appropriately	2.00	3.57	-1.57	NN
9. Have waxing/batik skill	1.70	3.86	-2.16	NN
10. Combine elements of design appropriately	1.63	3.66	-2.03	NN
11. Ability to do smocking	2.00	3.57	-1.57	NN
12. Ability to do beading	1.25	3.11	-2.06	NN
13. Embroidery by machine	3.70	1.48	2.33	SN
14. Have tie-dye skill	1.67	3.62	-1.95	NN
15. Ability to make quilt	3.62	1.67	1.95	SN
16. Ability to make patch-work	3.70	1.48	2.22	SN

N-340

Hint: NN = Not Needed

SN = Skill Needed

The result presented in Table 1 revealed that the mean responses of the skills possessed by home-economics students ranged from 1.26 to 3.86, while the mean responses of fabric designing skills needed by home-economics students ranged from 1.25 to 3.95. The value of the mean differences (\bar{X}_d) for skills possessed ranged from -2.16 to -1.57. The value of the mean differences (\bar{X}_d) for fabric designing skills needed ranged from 1.95 to 2.69. The result summarized in Table 1 showed that out of sixteen fabric designing skills identified, nine fabric designing skills having mean differences ranging from -2.16 to -1.57 thus are possessed by home-economics students, while seven fabric designing skills have mean differences ranging from 1.95 to 2.69 thus are needed by Home-economics

students. This is in line with Chan-klin (2014), who asserted that the current environment is characterized by rapid advancements in technology and media. Thus, students should be made to keep abreast of those technological changes for self-reliance, self-sufficiency, and to become employable.

Table 2: Analysis of the responses of the lecturers on the hindrances to acquiring these identified fabric designing skills by Home economics students in Southeast Nigeria, Universities. Page | 246

S/N	Hindrances to acquiring these skills	\bar{X} (means)	SD	Remarks
1	Inadequate basic fabric decoration equipment, tools, and fabrics in the laboratories	3.75	0.437	Agreed
2	Not using the supposed appropriate method of teaching practical	3.72	0.454	Agreed
3	Insufficient number of lecturers in the areas of clothing and textiles	3.36	0.537	Agreed
4	Lack of resourcefulness or innovation by clothing and textiles lecturers	3.53	0.536	Agreed
5	The rigidity of the lecturer	3.42	0.530	Agreed
6	Poor enterprise culture	3.83	0.524	Agreed
7	Discouragement of anything outside the prescribed pattern	3.75	0.437	Agreed
8	Lack of seed money for practical	3.42	0.743	Agreed
9	Non-inclusion of well-planned industrial training for the student in the curriculum	3.21	0.691	Agreed

N=60

Hint: SD = Standard Deviation \bar{X} (means) = Mean

In Table 2 above, the result thereof revealed that all the nine items have their mean values ranging from 3.21 to 3.83 and are above 2.50. The mean ranging from 3.21 to 3.83 is above 2.50 which is the decision cutoff point and is thus upheld by the respondents as some of the hindrances to acquiring fabric designing skills by Home-Economics students. This is in line with what several authors found out such as (Ewubare, 2010) who opined that inadequate facilities and equipment to cope with the number of students stifles the acquisition of skills amongst students and also insufficient laboratory

facilities compel Home Economics teachers/lecturers to use inappropriate methods of teaching and this makes learning delivery difficult. Also, (Ozioko, 2006) stated that some Home Economics lecturers in tertiary institutions do not like the teaching of clothing and textiles. On the issue of lack of seed money for practical, (Ewubare, 2010) pointed out that inadequate funding of tertiary institutions has often affected the teaching and learning of Home Economics amongst others. There is therefore need for these hindrances to be curbed to improve the versatility of the lecturers and also equip students with the knowledge, techniques, attitude, and manipulative skills needed for survival, and self-reliance and make them employable.

Table 3: Mean response of the lecturers on the ways these hindrances to acquiring these fabric designing skills by Home economics students in Southeast Nigeria, Universities can be solved.

S/N	Ways of curbing the hindrances	\bar{X} (means)	SD	Remarks
1	Provision of infrastructural facilities/textile items	3.75	0.427	Agreed
2	Employing more specialists in clothing and textiles area to handle the difficult areas	3.72	0.454	Agreed
3	Use of demonstration technique in teaching clothing and textiles aspects	3.50	0.537	Agreed
4	Organizing conferences, seminars, and workshops to upgrade the knowledge and skills of students and lecturers	3.33	0.536	Agreed
5	Sending students a real/ actual industrial training	3.42	0.530	Agreed
6	Embracing innovation	3.38	0.523	Agreed
7	In-service training of clothing and textiles lecturers	3.75	0.437	Agreed
8	Research	3.42	0,734	Agreed
9	Improvisation	3.22	0.691	Agreed
10	Improved school-industry relationship	3.77	0.427	Agreed
11	Use of AI Technologies	3.65	0.481	Agreed
12	Exhibition	3.57	0.500	Agreed
13	Marketing of products to encourage students	3.42	0.530	Agreed

N=60

Hint: SD = Standard Deviation \bar{X} (means) = Means

The data in Table 3 above revealed that all the items have their mean ranges from 3.22 to 3.77 and therefore are all above 2.50 which is the cutoff point.

Page | 248

Data analyzed for research question 3 showed that the mean ranging from 3.22 to 3.77 is above the decision cut-off point which is 2.5 thus, respondents agreed that for home-economics students to boost their finances all the thirteen ways found can help in improving Home economics students' dexterity in fabric designing. This is in line with Nwaokaomah (2010) who suggested that workshops and seminars should be encouraged in Home Economics courses to keep the teachers abreast with new trends in the use of equipment and machines, Ozioko (2006) wrote on improvisation that individuals should explore innovative ways to utilize existing resources and materials to create entirely new or improved versions of current goods and services. On the issue of funding, (Nwaokaomah, 2010) suggested that governmental bodies should assist tertiary institutions in funding the subject area as well as regular maintenance on the existing equipment to keep them in continuous working condition for effective learning amongst others. The findings of this study if practiced by home economics students will provide them with saleable skills that will make them become employable graduates and be able to boost their finances.

The implication of the study is that if the findings of this study is added to the thematic learning of home economics students and is practiced by them, will keep them abreast of the technological advancements in the society and thus provide them with salable skills that will help boost their finances. This study also has implications on curriculum design of home economics education, for its' incorporation will widen the skills to be acquired in the field of study. Also, it has implications on policy making which will aid in funding, upskilling of home economics personnel, implementation of designed curriculum, amongst others. It also implies that home economics students will be optimally employable if the findings of this study is practiced.

The study was limited to home economics students in the south eastern universities that have clothing and textiles. The suggestion for further study was on the availability and utilization of the fabric designing technologies. It was also suggested that this study to be replicated on other geo-political zones.

4. Conclusion

In a world that is constantly changing and technologically advancing, there is a need for home economics students to keep abreast with these changes. Also in an era where financial distress is the order of the day, there is a need for the students to be equipped with competency skills/21st century skills that will help them curb the effect of the distress by making them employable graduates or self-reliant. For this to be achievable, there is a need for constant improvement in the students' skill acquisition and this can be achieved by consistent and frequent research. In line with the findings, it is recommended that 21st-century skills be added to the thematic learning, and a well-organized industrial training scheme be mapped out for home economics students which they will be mandated to participate in for fostering industry-academia partnerships. Also, there is need for implementing the use of advanced technologies in the teaching and learning of home economics education. In as much as there is a need for advocacy for government funding of the universities, lecturers should be encouraged to practice improvisation more to curb the excesses of the government amongst others.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest

Author's Contributions

Conceptualization: UNN, NME

Formal Analysis: UNN

Investigation: UNN, NME

Methodology: UNN, NME

Writing of draft, review and editing: UNN, NME

Data Availability Statement

The article and supplementary materials contain the original contributions to the study, for further information, contact the authors.

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